

Influence of Social Media Platforms on Academic Performance of Business Education Students in Delta North Senatorial District of Delta State - Nigeria

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Abstract

This study examined the influence of social media platforms on academic performance of business education students in Delta North Senatorial District of Delta State - Nigeria. The aspect of social media platforms investigated were WhatsApp and YouTube. Similarly, the moderating influence of gender, was also investigated. Two research questions were raised and answered, while two null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance. The descriptive survey research design was adopted. The population of the study was 388 undergraduate students from Federal College of Education (Tech), Asaba and University of Delta, Agbor. The simple random sampling technique was employed and the sample size was 232. The instrument for data collection was the questionnaire. The instrument was face and content validated by three experts from Department of Business Education and Measurement and Evaluation Unit of the Delta State University, Abraka. The overall reliability coefficient of 0.82 was obtained. Data collected were analyzed using Mean, Standard Deviation and t-test Statistics. Findings of the study revealed that the usage of WhatsApp and YouTube has positive influence on the Business education students' academic performance. Also, that there is no significant difference between the mean response of male and female Business Education students on the influence of social media on academic performance. The study concluded that social media does influences Business Education students' academic performance in tertiary institutions in Delta North Senatorial District. The study recommended amongst others that institutions of higher learning should put in place facilities like a functioning and effective Internet service to support the use of social media platform for academic purposes by the Business Education students.

Keywords: Social Medial Platforms, Academic Performance, Business Education, WhatsApp, YouTube

Introduction

Education is highly ranked in the agenda of the 21st century nations. It is the art of acquiring knowledge, developing of the reasoning and judgmental abilities of the mind, character and manipulative competencies in a formal setting. Education can authoritatively be regarded as the key to national development because it unravels the economic potentials of the masses, strengthens and equips individuals in the society to fully engage and benefit from their national cake. Education is important to the development of human resources, impartation of appropriate skills, knowledge and attitudes. Education plays an unquantifiable role in the society, nation and the global world at large. It is the only instrument that liberates and protects the human rights through a well detailed and acquired knowledge. Ajuluchukwu (2015) sees education as the best avenue which destroys timidity, idleness, joblessness and creates awareness of healthy living among individuals.

Education is generally acknowledged as being crucial for the advancement process of any nation. That is the reason why Nigerian educational policy makers and social planners have placed a huge premium on the development of the education sector (Olakulehin, 2007). Globally, it has been acknowledged that education of the citizenry is a strategic factor for sustainable development in any country. The significance of education in the under developed countries of the world is on the rise because they have acknowledged the necessity to meet up with the advanced countries when it comes to the engagement of social media openings.

Academic performance entails the different means students respond to their academic materials assigned by their teachers/lecturers. This explains that high academic performance is directly connected and measured by the examination results. This study therefore attempts to decipher how some social media outlets influences the performance of business education

students academically in Delta North Senatorial District of Delta State. Business Education is a term that covers series of techniques employed in mentoring students on the essentials of business strategies. These methods extend from the instructional degree courses like Masters of Business Administration (MBA), to school towards opportunity system on comparative education. Business Education is a major component of vocational education. A designed area of study for the mastering and enhancement of skills, acceptable manners, appreciation, inquisitiveness, as well as availability of awareness and competencies in the office work and business world.

Social media is a combination of interest-based applications and platforms which permits its users to create contents, share videos, audios and allows interactions with multiple user' s same time. Examples of social media platforms include Twitter, Facebook, WhatsApp, Togo, Google, YouTube, Instagram, Snapchat, Pinterest, Websites, Television, Radio, zoom and so on. However, this study will be limited to two social media platforms, WhatsApp and YouTube. According to Igberaharha O. C. (2015), since the inception of social media especially the expansion of communicative packages, it has enhanced the procedure for acquiring knowledge process which is gradually gaining ground mostly among university students. Social Media entails so many positive impacts as well as unfavorable implications on the responses of students academically.

The use of Twitter, Facebook, WhatsApp and YouTube for example has enhanced the performance of students academically especially in their external examinations, these social media platforms enable students develop independent learning abilities, and these students are able to digest the lecturer' s explanations in their informal settings, self-orientations, time and space. They independently seek peer assistance and collaborations from social media in relation to their learning activities.

The WhatsApp platform helps to connect teachers and their students through chat groups created where information, and instructional contents are shared without physical gathering of the parties, there is room for questions from students pertaining to the learning contents by the teacher, corresponding feedback from the teacher and assignments where applicable (Lenhart 2007). These students also engage in WhatsApp voice notes, video and audio calls for easy understanding and assimilation of the learning materials. This social media platform affords students the opportunity of asking relevant questions relating to their learning. WhatsApp is a platform having collaborative features such as the capacity to exchange text messages, images, videos, and voice notes to their social network or group and contacts. Shuayb and Gebreel (2021) carried out research on effect of using WhatsApp on academic grades of users. The findings of the research show that using social media (WhatsApp) by students can be of a favorable and effective effects on their academic performance.

The YouTube platform on the other hand, present students with educative videos, audio visual materials, photographs, images and shot clips thereby expanding their horizons and helping them to combine theoretical learning with practical (Khatri, 2020). Vethamani (2004) conducted a study on YouTube and found that YouTube exposes students to use current technology in studying a course; also, connect learners to several reading contents provided in electronic form and other students with similarities in their purpose; and that it encourages communication links in learning unlike the traditional forms of communications like the audiotape and television that had non-interactive forms. Apparently, YouTube permits so many people to learn, watch and distribute originally prepared videos. It also provides a medium for users to associate, get informed and motivate other users globally while acting as a platform for disseminating information for original-content marketers. Web

sites allow individuals to develop personal pages which can be general or closed bounded patterns and also provides the features to connect, share information and communicate with people (friends or strangers) on the internet within the international or local scale.

Talaue, AlSaad, AlRushaidan, AlHugail, & AlFahhad, (2018) carried out study on impact of social media on academic performance of selected college students. In their study, they noted that YouTube have a two – faced effect on student progress, and important to approach students’ use of it with complete responsibility. Also, Mushtaq (2018) conducted a study on the effects of social media on the undergraduate students’ academic performances. The study found that the positive impacts of YouTube among the undergraduates appeared to be higher as compared to negative impacts.

This study however, investigated the moderating variable of gender. Gender refers to male and female. It is the features of boys, girls, men, and women that are socially constructed. Akpojotor (2022) conducted a study on digitalization of business education programme in Tertiary institutions in Delta State, Nigeria: Challenges and Prospects. The study uses the moderating variable of gender. The findings of the work revealed that there was no significant difference between the mean ratings of the demographic variables of business education lecturers on the department’ s digitalization prospects. Nwazor and Godwin- Maduiké (2015) investigated social media platforms and the findings of the study revealed that learner’ s involvement in the cyberspace leads to a low turnout of production, wrong use of words and a decrease in research abilities, indulging in juvenile activities harmful to academic activities. Their study emphasizes the consistency and addiction on the internet by students form the major causes of low grades in English studies both in internal and external assessment exercises among students in secondary schools in South – East Nigeria.

Consequently, it has been observed that frequent commitment to the internet results to negligence of closeness and bonding in the family and also decrease in interactions in the family. It is noted that children in homes who are isolated and attached to various social media platforms care less about interaction with family members, family relationships thereby leaving the sittings rooms to login a spot, concentrating fully to their phones, engage in chats with short forms of words believing that social media platforms are informal settings hence, their use of slangs and coded languages do not matter but overtime, they begin to transcend these wrong vocabularies into their school learnings and end up speaking and writing wrong grammatical sentences in their examinations (Krampah & Frempong-Kore, 2021). This may affect their academic performance in their examinations. Again, these students also tend to participate in social media mostly at night leading to sleep deprivation and its attendant consequences. These and so many other negative variables attached to the engagement in the internet space may adversely influence student' s output academically. It is against this background that the researcher has decided to find out the influence of social media platforms on academic performance of business education students in Delta North Senatorial District of Delta State - Nigeria

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What are the influences of WhatsApp on the academic results of business education students in Delta North Senatorial District of Delta State?
2. What are the influences of YouTube on the academic performance of business education students in Delta North Senatorial District of Delta State?

Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses guided the study at 0.05 level of significance

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Ho₁: There is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female respondents on the influences of WhatsApp on the academic responses of business education students.

Ho₂: The mean responses of male and female respondents do not differ significantly on the influences of YouTube on the academic performance of business education students.

Methods

The descriptive survey design was used in this study and the population consist of 388 students studying business education from the 2022/2023 academic session which is composed of 304 students from Federal College of Education (T), Asaba and 84 students from University of Delta, Agbor respectively. The sample size was 232 business education students. The simple random sampling method was used for the study. Questionnaire was used as for data collection. The instrument was validated by three experts, two in the Department of Business Education and one in Measurement and Evaluation, at Delta State University, Abraka. Mean and standard deviation were applied in answering the two research questions on a benchmark of 2.50; while t-test statistic was employed in testing the two null hypotheses tested at 0.05 levels of significance. The decision made for the research question was established on the basis that any calculated Mean (\bar{x}) that was below 2.50 means disagreed and any calculated Mean (\bar{x}) that was 2.50 and above means agreed. The decision point on the hypotheses was based on 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, any calculated p-value that is greater than 0.5, the null hypotheses was accepted and when any calculated p-value is lesser than 0.05, the null hypothesis was rejected.

Results and Discussion

Research Question One

What influences does WhatsApp have on the academic grades of business education students in Delta North Senatorial District of Delta State?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation responses on effects of WhatsApp on Academic performance of students offering Business Education. (N=232)

S/N	Statement	X	SD	Remark
1	Easy accessibility of WhatsApp by students offering business education help to increase their academic achievements.	2.66	0.85	Agreed
2	WhatsApp allows in the field of business education to create group chats for easy communication which influence their academic performance	2.80	0.97	Agreed
3	WhatsApp enable users to share videos, documents, images, class materials, assignment and other educational resources which promote their results academically.	2.79	0.97	Agreed
4	Lecturers in business education uses WhatsApp to post messages to students about important notifications, upcoming events or deadlines, and updates which help to upgrade students' academic results.	2.83	0.96	Agreed
5	With WhatsApp, sharing of content like Audio, Video and document which may enhance students' academic result is made easy.	2.84	0.96	Agreed
6	WhatsApp can easily help in communicating with parents and to give update about their students' growth. This helps in influencing the students' academic achievements.	2.82	0.97	Agreed

7	The engagement of WhatsApp encourages collaboration between students' business education.	2.89	0.94	Agreed
8	Private studies using WhatsApp influence students' academic responses.	2.88	0.95	Agreed
9	WhatsApp habitual usage enhance better academic grades for students	2.85	0.95	Agreed
10	Communicating through WhatsApp platform can boost students' expressive ability, thereby enhance their academic performance.	2.83	0.96	Agreed
	Cluster Mean/SD	2.82	0.95	Agreed

Table 1 revealed that respondents agreed to all items measuring the influence of WhatsApp as it regards to academic enhancement. Also, this is reflected in the mean score of 2.82 and standard deviation of 0.95 which is above the mean benchmark of 2.50 for region of acceptance. The standard deviation portrayed that participants are not far apart in their responses. Hence, the engagement of WhatsApp does influence the performance of students academically.

Research Question Two

What are the influences of YouTube on the academic performance of students studying business education in Delta North Senatorial District of Delta State?

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation responses on influence of YouTube on Academic performance

S/N	Statement	X	SD	Remark
11	Using YouTube videos in the teaching courses in the field business enhances students' academic excellence	2.96	0.87	Agreed
12	YouTube help students in the field of business education to expand their listening skills which help in enhancing their performance	2.94	0.87	Agreed

	academically.			
13	With activities in YouTube, students can see how practical are carried out, thereby enhancing their academic responses	2.85	0.84	Agreed
14	Students form group on YouTube and post content that will be beneficial to all members of the group and in turn influence their academic performance	2.88	0.84	Agreed
15	YouTube provides access to a wide range of educational content from experts in the field which help students in the field of education to improve their academic performance	2.89	0.86	Agreed
16	YouTube provides clips that helps in learning some courses or topics.	2.90	0.86	Agreed
17	YouTube fosters students' involvement in self-directed learning.	2.90	0.85	Agreed
18	Students offering business education who have issue concentrating on a particular thing for an extended time might benefit from this online education.	2.86	0.87	Agreed
19	Student who uses YouTube in academic endeavors watch more films that enhance their academic grades	2.93	0.85	Agreed
20	Some students studying business education divert some monies meant for their academic materials into buying data for watching YouTube	2.81	0.86	Agreed
	Cluster Mean/SD	2.89	0.86	Agreed

Table 2 revealed that respondents agreed to the items measuring the influence of YouTube on the students' academic performance. This is reflected in the mean score of 2.89 and standard deviation of 0.86 which is above mean benchmark of 2.50 for region of acceptance. Standard deviation reflects that respondents are not far apart in their responses. Hence, YouTube usage influences Business Education students' academic performance.

Hypothesis One

There is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female respondents on the influences of WhatsApp on the academic performance of business education students.

Table 3: *t-test Analysis of Male and Female Respondents' Mean Ratings on influence of WhatsApp on Academic Performance*

Variable	N	Mean	SD	df	α	t	p-value	Decision
Male	76	2.51	0.81	230	0.05	-1.833	0.07	NS
Female	156	2.73	0.87					

Table 3 showed t-test statistical analysis between male and female Business Education students with regards to WhatsApp usage influence on academic performance. The observed t-value is -1.833 while p-value was 0.07. Consequently, critical t-value of 1.96 is greater than observed t-value and the p-value is greater than alpha value of 0.05. Thus, null hypothesis was accepted. Therefore, there is no significant difference between the mean response of male and female students on influence of WhatsApp on academic performance.

Hypothesis two

There is no obvious difference in the mean responses of male and female respondents on the influences of YouTube on the academic performance of business education students.

Table 4: *t-test Analysis of Male and Female Respondents' Mean Ratings on influence of YouTube on Academic Performance*

Variable	N	Mean	SD	df	α	t	p-value	Decision
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Male	76	2.51	0.81	230	0.05	-1.833	0.068	NS
Female	156	2.73	0.87					

Table 4 showed t-test statistical analysis between male and female Business Education students with regards to YouTube usage influence on academic performance. From observed t-value of -1.833 and the critical t-value of 1.96, it can be deduced that since the observed t-value is lesser to critical t-value, and observed p-value is bigger compared to the alpha value of 0.05, the null hypothesis was accepted. So, no tangible difference between mean response of male and female students on impact of YouTube on academic behavior.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of research question one emphasizes that WhatsApp usage has influence on Business Education students' academic performance. From the findings it was also revealed that Easy accessibility of WhatsApp by business education students help to increase their academic performance. WhatsApp allows students studying business education to create group chats for easy communication which influence academic results. The use of WhatsApp encourages collaboration between business education students and that communication using WhatsApp boost students' ability to express themselves, thereby help to enhance their performance academically.

This finding aligns with work of Shuayb and Gebreel (2021) who carried out research on effect of using WhatsApp on academic grades of users. Study shows that using social media (WhatsApp) by students can be of a favorable and effective effects on their academic performance. The finding from hypothesis one shows that there is no significant difference between the mean response of male and female students on the influence of WhatsApp on academic performance. The finding from this research concurs with the work of Akpojotor

(2022) who discovered that there was no significant difference between the mean ratings of the demographic variables of business education lecturers on the department' s digitalization prospects.

The finding of this study also agrees with the work by Nwazor and Godwin – Maduiké (2015) which concludes that learner' s involvement in the cyberspace leads to a low turnout of production, wrong use of words and a decrease in research abilities, indulging in juvenile activities harmful to academic activities. Their study emphasizes the consistency and addiction on the internet by students form the major causes of low grades in English studies both in internal and external assessment exercises among students in secondary schools in South – East Nigeria.

The findings of research question two reveals that the engagement of YouTube videos in the teaching of business education enhance students' academic results; YouTube help students offering business education to upgrade their listening skills which aids in enhancing their academic performance; With YouTube. The finding is in harmony with the findings of Vethamani (2004) which affirmed that YouTube exposes students to use current technology in studying a course; also, connect learners to many reading contents provided in electronic form and other students with similarities in their purpose; and that it encourages communication links in learning unlike the traditional forms of communications like the audiotape and television that had non-interactive forms.

Finding from hypothesis two reveals that there is no noticeable difference between the mean response of male and female learners on the influence of YouTube on academic performance in Business Education. This finding aligned with the study by Talaue, et al. (2018) who reviewed the impact of social media on academic grade of certain college students. In their study, they noted that YouTube have a two – faced effect on student

progress, and important to approach students' use of it with complete responsibility. Also, this current study is in agreement with the work of Mushtaq (2018) on the effects of social media on the undergraduate students' academic performances. The study observed that the positive impacts of YouTube among the undergraduates appeared to be higher as compared to negative impacts. The study also reveals no statistically significant differences between positive and negative effect of social media and students' academic results; giving credence to the point that even though researches have shown YouTube usage positively influences academic excellence, it should be moderated as one can easily drift from its benefit to its disadvantages in one's academic height pursuit. The implication here is that learners ought to be effectively mentored and updated on consequences of not appropriately utilizing the privileges attached to the inception of YouTube platforms.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, when WhatsApp and YouTube are properly utilized and employed for educational purposes, it could be a veritable avenue for knowledge acquisition with attendant implications on enhanced academic performance of students but when employed otherwise, it is capable of derailing students from academic paths. Therefore, it was concluded that social media does influences Business Education students' academic performance in tertiary institutions in Delta North Senatorial District.

Recommendations

- i. Government and the relevant authorities especially the Business Education department should employ the social media openings in the pedagogical process with a view to imbibing its tenet on students for them to reap the huge benefits inherent in its usage.

- ii. Institutions of higher learning should put in place facilities like a functioning and effective Internet service to support the use of social media platform for academic purposes by the Business Education students.
- iii. Students should not abuse social media channels since its abuse and addiction can negatively affect students' academic grades.

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